

SafeHabitus

Deliverable 1.6

Understanding farm safety and farmer health challenges in the EU

Batch 2 of EIP-Agri Practice Abstracts

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Acronyms

The list of acronyms presented below is specific to the text presented in the introduction.

AKIS: Agricultural Knowledge Innovation System

CoP: Community of Practice

EU: European Union

FHS: Farm Health and Safety

FHS KIS: Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System

MAA: Multi-actor Approach

NPD: National Policy Dialogue

PA: Practice Abstract

SEM: Socioecological Model

SH: SafeHabitus

TN: Technical Note

Acknowledgements

The knowledge presented in this Deliverable represents inputs from the 11 Community of Practice (CoP) partners in the SafeHabitus project. Each CoP is led by a project partner who, collectively, have brought together over 180 farm safety and farmer health experts in support of the development of the Practice Abstracts presented in this report. In addition to thanking the individual authors of the Practice Abstracts, we extend our heartfelt appreciation to the members of the CoPs who contributed their time, knowledge and expertise. Their support has resulted in the creation of knowledge that highlights the diversity of farm safety and farmer/worker health needs across the EU.

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Introduction

SafeHabitus is a multi-actor project that seeks to strengthen Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System (FHS KIS) and support the EU transition to social sustainability in farming. The SafeHabitus approach recognises that whilst enhancing awareness and understanding of risks and hazards is one part of the solution, it is not the only, nor indeed the most effective solution to the health and safety challenge, particularly when many of the unsafe or unhealthy behaviours are habitual¹. Overcoming this challenge requires not only awareness raising regarding risks and hazards but also a systematic approach - one that has the farmer or worker at the centre, supported by the community of stakeholders who can support them to adopt safer and healthier practices².

This report presents the second set of Practice Abstracts developed as part of the work programme of the SafeHabitus Communities of Practice (CoPs). It provides an overview of the structure of national level policy and governance frameworks, an evaluation of farmer perspectives and priorities for farm safety, and a multi-actor assessment of the root causes and consequences of farm injuries in 11 EU member states who are represented by partners in the SafeHabitus consortium (Figure 1). The member states and associated partners were selected based representing the diversity of EU agriculture.

Each CoP, facilitated by a consortium member, consists of farmers and institutions, businesses and other actors that function as knowledge brokers in the AKIS. This enables SafeHabitus to go beyond the state of the art by moving away from generic efforts to improve FHS amongst farmers and workers and draw on the group's expertise to respond to end-user needs by developing practical innovations that engage and support farmers to take action.

Figure 1. SafeHabitus Communities of Practice

¹ Kwasnicka, D., Dombrowski, S.U., White, M. and Sniehotta, F., 2016. Theoretical explanations for maintenance of behaviour change: a systematic review of behaviour theories. *Health Psychology Review*, 10(3), pp.277-296

² O'Connor, T., Kinsella, J., McNamara, J., O'Hora, D. and Meredith, D., 2021. Learning through design using collaborative Intervention Mapping with acceptability evaluation: the case of a group-based farm safety intervention. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 27(3), pp.403-420.

Methods - Developing the Practice Abstracts

Work Package 2 of the SafeHabitus project implements a Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) through the establishment of 11 CoPs that engage 180 FHS actors and stakeholders to share knowledge, enhance understanding of the nature of farm safety challenges and support the co-creation of practical solutions to farm health and safety issues³. Following the establishment of the CoP, a 'Needs Register' was developed, and issues, needs and good practices identified and reported in the 78 Technical Notes and 56 Practice abstracts summarized in the SafeHabitus Deliverable 1.5. and published in the SafeHabitus KnowledgeHub. These previous works described local contexts in the CoP countries, the safety issues in European agriculture and, more importantly, collated potential solutions and good practices to address these safety challenges. This work has been now expanded through analysing national policy and governance frameworks and shaping recommendations on strengthening them (11 PAs), identifying key safety challenges and related causal and consequential factors (11 PAs), and farm safety priorities of farming populations across Europe (11 PAs). In addition, one PA on implementation of Social Conditionality in the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and one PA introducing the Irish tax policy system which accelerates farm safety investments have been produced.

Practice Abstract (PA) 8 describes Task 2.3: Mapping the Farm Health and Safety Knowledge and Innovation System (FHS KIS). This task aimed to identify and analyse national and regional policy and governance frameworks that shape farm health and safety across the 11 EU Member States represented in SafeHabitus. Each national Community of Practice (CoP) carried out a guided, participatory actor mapping exercise that visualised the actors within the FHS KIS framework and assessed their level of importance, interest, and influence. This map was further evaluated and updated during the first National Policy Dialogue (NPD). The NPD also evaluated the functioning of the FHS KIS in term of coordination, leadership, and collaboration within the framework.

The outcome of these activities is described in Technical Note (TN) 8, produced by each CoP. This TN 8 details the actors, their influence on and interest in FHS, missing actors, and actors who could play a stronger role. Insights from the guided evaluation during the first national Policy Dialogue informed a better understanding of coordination, leadership, collaboration, and farmer engagement. This helped to shape recommendations to strengthen national FHS policy and governance.

This TN formed the basis for the PA 8 which summarises the context and rationale, outlines the methodology, and presents recommendations to strengthen the framework. The process was coordinated by Teagasc, with support from all CoP partners (ZRC SAZU, Oxfam, SVLFG, BEC, IDELE, VDU, Savonia, LBU, UAK, EULS, Teagasc) and Luke (WP 2 leader) ensuring a coherent approach while allowing for adaptation to the national context.

Practice Abstract 9 describes Task 3.2: Understanding the causes and consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges. The objective of this task is to identify the root causes and wider consequences of critical farm health and safety challenges identified by 11 Communities of Practice across the EU, as well as potential solutions. This involved CoP countries each holding Expert focus groups or interviews (in some cases supported by further data collection) that apply the Socioecological Model (SEM) to identify wider social and contextual factors surrounding farm safety challenges.

The findings and applications of these activities are reported in each CoP's TN 9. Each country's report describes a key safety challenge, the research methodology, outlines the main causal and

³ For more information on the SH MAA see Annex 1 of Deliverable 2.1 *Baseline monitoring and evaluation report*

consequential factors for this key safety challenge, and provides a social ecological analysis that includes potential solutions. These Technical Notes provide important empirical insights into the socioeconomic, political, and organisational characteristics of farm safety across Europe. PA 9 then summarises this TN 9 to describe a condensed overview of the key safety challenge addressed and methodology used in order to highlight the main findings of this research. The process was coordinated by Teagasc to allow all CoP partners (ZRC SAZU; Oxfam; BEC; IDELE; VDU; Savonia; LBU; UAK; Teagasc; EULS; SVLFG) to conduct this research on a nationally farm safety challenge while maintaining academic rigour throughout.

Practice Abstract 10 describes Task 3.4: Co-designing approaches to increase engagement of specific agricultural production sectors and populations with risk management tools. The objective of this task is to collaborate with CoPs to identify the farm safety and engagement priorities of different farming populations across Europe in order to inform future and ongoing safety interventions and knowledge transfer. This task involved CoP's each conducting a two-question survey in their country to identify farmer, family member, agricultural student, and farmworker's ranked farm safety and engagement priorities. Then CoP leaders organised an expert evaluation of national survey results to identify any relevant implications and implementation strategies.

The combined findings from this survey and expert evaluations are reported in each CoP's TN 10. Each country's report describes an overview of how the current national farm safety system engages farmers, the findings of the survey (including demographics and farmers safety and engagement priorities), and the expert's evaluation. These Technical Notes synthesise evidence from end-users and experts on how to improve national engagement with diverse farming populations. PA 10 then summarises this TN 10 to describe a condensed overview of the survey results and expert evaluation to highlight the main findings of this research. The process was coordinated by Teagasc to allow all CoP partners (ZRC SAZU; Oxfam; BEC; IDELE; VDU; Savonia; LBU; UAK; Teagasc; EULS; SVLFG) to conduct a scientifically rigorous and contextually sensitive empirical survey.

SafeHabitus

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Estonia

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Estonia

Issue: Estonia's farm health and safety (FHS) framework is fragmented, with no single coordinating body. Responsibilities are divided between ministries, the Labour Inspectorate, and advisory services. While small and micro-farms (~90% of farms) have limited financial resources to follow OHS requirements, the Estonian Government plan to cut the employer assignments in law. Training, safety guidelines, and networking between stakeholders are limited, reducing the effectiveness of FHS policies and risk prevention measures.

Method: SafeHabitus applied a structured approach to map FHS governance in Estonia, using desk research, web-based stakeholder identification, expert interviews, CoP (EstCoP) meetings, National Policy Dialogues, conferences, training courses, and virtual networks. An Influence-Interest-Engagement matrix guided actor mapping, visualizing actors' roles in shaping FHS.

Results: The process identified key stakeholders with high responsibility and influence, including government ministries, regulatory bodies, farmers' unions, research and educational institutions, and advisory services. Training and NPD discussions highlighted gaps in legislative adaptation, risk awareness, and farmer engagement. Recommendations aim to strengthen FHS by increasing visibility, integrating FHS training into education, updating legislation, establishing accident/illness recording and compensation systems, using the OiRA e-tool, and ensuring accessible online information. The multi-actor approach enhances coordination, supports evidence-informed policy, and promotes safer, more resilient agricultural communities.

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Target Audience

Target group 1: Policymakers, public authorities

Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Researchers

Understanding the Causes and Consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges: Occupational accidents among female workers handling livestock/dairy cattle

Issue: This study explores the causes and consequences of occupational accidents among female workers in Estonia's livestock sector, particularly dairy farming, one of the country's most hazardous occupations. Between 2015 and 2024, 1,429 agricultural accidents were recorded, over half in the dairy sector, with women disproportionately affected (63%).

Method: The research applied a socio-ecological model using a focus group of five female professionals with farming experience to identify individual, interpersonal, organisational, community, and policy-level factors contributing to accidents and to explore animal-related occupational accidents among female workers. The discussion addressed three themes: causes, consequences, and possible safety interventions.

Results: At the individual level, accidents stem from fatigue, stress, poor awareness, and unsafe positioning near animals. Interpersonal issues include weak supervision and poor communication, while organizational risks arise from inadequate facility design, long hours, and staff shortages. Community traditions often undervalue formal safety practices, and policy gaps leave livestock-specific and gender-sensitive risks insufficiently addressed. Consequences are not only physical injuries but also psychological effects such as fear, guilt, and reduced confidence. Recommendations include gender-aware safety training, better-designed facilities, improved supervision, open communication, and policy reforms reflecting the specific risks of livestock work.

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Target Audience

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Target group 2: Public authorities, rural development organisations

Target group 3: Researchers

An evaluated survey on 'Risk management and support for Estonian farmers'

Issue: This practice abstract summarizes the findings of a 2025 national survey on risk management and support for Estonian farmers, exploring how they perceive workplace safety, risks, and training needs. Although agriculture employs a small portion of Estonia's workforce, it remains among the most dangerous sectors, with frequent injuries involving livestock and machinery. Despite this, there is no dedicated national farm safety strategy or systematic coordination between key ministries.

Method: The 2025 survey gathered 52 responses through online and printed questionnaires distributed by agricultural advisors and Community of Practice (CoP) members. All participants were over 18 and gave informed consent.

Results: Study revealed that raising awareness of health and safety risks was seen as the top priority for safer farm work, followed by use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and safe machinery. Farmers valued structured, expert-led training - classroom courses, peer discussions, and one-on-one advice - over informal learning or online tools. Community of Practice (CoP) reflections noted that while results mainly reflected managers' perspectives, more input from smallholders and workers would add balance. Stakeholders also observed that although farmers prioritized "awareness," funding and access to modern equipment are often the real foundations for safety improvements.

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Finland

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Finland

Issue: The occupational-based social security in agriculture is divided based on entrepreneurship or work contract: for agricultural entrepreneurs, i.e. farmers, insurance and services are provided by the Farmers' Social Insurance Institution Mela. Hired workers are covered by any insurance company providing occupational accident and disease insurance and benefit from strong occupational health and safety legislation. This separation means farmers are largely outside general OHS legislation, creating a complex governance landscape with many actors involved in FHS.

Method: SafeHabitus developed a structured method to map farm health and safety governance, which each country applied and adapted to its context. In Finland, this involved desk research, a Community of Practice meeting, and evaluation as part of the National Policy Dialogue. The actor mapping showed a high number of actors in FHS, but there's need for improved FHS coordination.

Results:

Develop a FHS strategy that covers both farmers' and hired workers in agriculture with comprehensive development plan of the FHS. The strategy process should involve all main actors in FHS.

Develop the accessibility, affordability, and relevance of the Occupational Health Care Services to better meet farmers' needs.

Ensuring sustained funding for research and development of FHS to support evidence-based improvements.

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Researchers

Farmer's view on occupational safety

Issue: Despite continuous efforts to enhance occupational safety, accidents in agriculture remain prevalent. This research investigates occupational safety challenges from the farmers' perspective in Finland, focusing on the Farmer Health and Safety Needs Register ([Finland](#)).

Two key categories of safety risks are explored:

- **Physical, Chemical, and Biological Hazards:** These include risks related to Arctic farming conditions, machinery operation, animal handling, use of personal protective equipment (PPE), slips and falls, forestry activities, automation, and the need for adequate training in digital tools and safety culture.
- **Health Risks:** These include work-related stress, long hours, mental well-being, motivation, and the physical impact of tasks leading to musculoskeletal diseases (MSDs), respiratory issues, skin conditions, and other chronic health concerns.

Method: The interview structure was developed jointly between student researchers and the FinCoP administrator. A thematic interview approach was used, combining three main themes, each containing one main question and several supporting sub-questions. Students used semi-structured interviews that employed a conversational approach with flexibility in question phrasing and order. Sub-questions were used to draw out more detailed responses when initial answers were brief or limited. This study was conducted with the sample of seven farmers. A qualitative research design was chosen to capture experiences and insights from the participants in their individual context.

Results: The findings from the thematic interviews reveal that farmers understand the occupational hazards present in their work and are generally aware of potential risk factors. They demonstrated the ability to anticipate dangerous situations and identify safety risks. However, significant variability in safety practices was identified across farms. There was no standardized operational model that all farmers applied, leading to diverse approaches to occupational safety.

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Target group 2: Public authorities, rural development organisations

Target group 3: Researchers

Finnish farms highest priorities for making a farm safer and ways how farmers prefer to learn about farm safety

Issue: Finnish farming faces safety and health challenges despite a long-term decline in injury rates (The Finnish Farmers' Social Insurance Institution Mela statistics). This research investigates farms highest priorities for making a farm safer and ways how farmers prefer to learn about farm safety.

Method: This survey data is based directly on Dairy barometer 2024, a survey that was carried out in 2024 by Savonia University of Applied Sciences with dairy co-operative Maitosuomi. Dairy farmers filled it out by using the digital Webropol - tool. Questions from survey were identified that closely matched the English-language items and analysed accordingly. All of 138 replies were taken into this report.

Results: Personal protective equipment (PPE) were considered the most important priority for farm safety, followed by improving awareness of health and safety risks. Ensuring safe machinery and equipment ranks third. Factors such as financial resources, external training support, having help on the farm and support from family and friends were less important. The most preferred method to learn about farm safety is participating in formal training courses or classroom settings. Learning through practical experience and peer discussions were also rank highly. One-to-one specialist support is moderately preferred. Reading materials, risk assessment tools and informal discussions with family and friends are less favored as primary learning methods.

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP France

Strengthening the FHS Policy and Governance Framework in France

Issue: The French farm health and safety (FHS) framework is well structured. Many actors are involved in delivering five years' strategic and prevention occupational health and safety plans (OHS) and in assessing them. Public authorities are fully involved, feedback is collected from the field, and bottom-up processes are promoted to identify and capitalise actions. However, some could play a larger role.

Method: SafeHabitus developed a structured method to map FHS policy and governance and key actors. In France, this involved desk-based research (literature review, meeting with Community of Practice (CoP) members and an interview with a MSA advisor) then a CoP meeting as part of the National Policy Dialogue to map and assess the framework. The mapping showed strong connections among actors. Farmers are involved but to varying degrees, mostly through their unions and local MSA. Occupational health and safety research organisations could be more active in agricultural sector, as could banks and other financial organisations.

Results: Improvement lies in better engaging and coordinating existing actors, rather than adding new ones. Strengthening bottom-up feedback, sharing good practices beyond MSA, and fostering peer-to-peer learning can drive change. Linking work practices and organisations to health outcomes and involving diverse stakeholders—advisors, educators, farmers—will enhance impact. Emphasising FHS as vital for well-being, not just regulation, and integrating into education can shift mindsets and improve long-term safety.

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Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Researchers

Understanding the causes and consequences of accidents involving cattle handlers in France

Issue: The accident rate is almost twice as high on farms with cattle compared to other farms. Aim is to identify the factors leading to cattle-handling accidents and the consequences of these incidents, distinguishing between several levels of analysis such as the individual, interpersonal, organizational, community and policy levels.

Method: An interview was realised with an MSA advisor included three sections: causes of accidents; consequences of accidents and potential solutions to improve FHS. A discussion group focused on ergonomics and the causes of animal-related incidents brought together 10 participants from Idele and Prévent'Agri.

Results: By combining the reflections of the group and the MSA advisor, 22 codes about causes were generated: 7 individual, 5 interpersonal, 8 organizational, 1 community and 2 political. Individual contributing factors may be related to the farmer's experience or their perception of animal behaviour. At the Interpersonal and organizational level causes can be link with human-animal relationship, infrastructure design, or economic constraints. The consequences of accidents extend beyond physical injuries, with psychological, social, and economic repercussions for farmers and their families. To mitigate these risks, the proposed solutions emphasize training and prevention.

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Target group 3: Researchers

French farmers' safety and engagement priorities

Issue: Farm safety is a critical issue for farmers and their families. The SafeHabitus project which seeks to improve farm safety across Europe, created a survey with 3 questions to better understanding of farmer's needs to improve safety.

Method: The survey was translated in coordination with the French CoP to ensure no dramatic alteration of the survey's meaning to fit our local context. There are 65 surveys return: 31 in France and 34 in Wallonia. 24 surveys were filled out online and 41 collected on paper of which 34 from training sessions conducted by PreventAgri (Wallonia)

Results: Financial and technical options come first when respondents rank agricultural safety and risk management priorities from a list of seven options. However, there are some differences of response between men and women, that may link to the gendered distribution of professional tasks. Participants rank their preferred methods of engagement with risk management and farm safety information from a list of six options. Exchanges between peers or with a specialist/advisor comes as first options for men and women, which supports the current approach. CoP discussions highlight the additional importance of primary prevention.

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Target group 3: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Germany

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Germany

Issue: Germany has a dual Occupational health and Safety (OHS) system: state law and statutory accident insurance work together. In farming, the SVLFG leads prevention, advice and supervision. Many actors endorse safety, yet day-to-day action is often handed over to the SVLFG. Responsibility and identification with OHS on farms and in sector bodies is limited, and visibility on social media is low.

Method: SafeHabitus applied a structured mapping of farm health and safety governance using an Importance-Influence-Interest matrix and the Quadruple Helix. In Germany, this included desk research, an expert workshop at SVLFG, Community of Practice discussions, and evaluation during the National Policy Dialogue at Green Week 2025 in Berlin. The mapping showed that most stakeholders place themselves high interest/high influence, with few taking consistent practical action.

Results: Based on these findings, several practical recommendations have been identified to strengthen farm health and safety governance and engagement:
Treat safety as a shared task, not an external duty.
Use SVLFG self-administration to drive awareness evolution, peer learning and farm-level uptake. Review rules and tools for practical effect and cut bureaucracy.
Claim support roles of social partners, advisers, schools and ministries.
Invest in targeted campaigns, hands-on training and demos.
Engage credible farm influencers to reach younger audiences.
Enforce action that matches agricultural culture to raise awareness of safety.

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Target Audience

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Target group 3: Researchers

Making tractor seat belt use easy and routine

Issue: Tractors are safer with ROPS and a seat belt. Yet many drivers do not buckle up. Surveys and interviews show why: lap belts feel tight, restrict movement, and are impractical for short, stop-start tasks. Use on public roads is also low. Safety experts confirm that belts keep the driver inside the cab and within the protective space during a roll-over. But most machines have basic lap belts or ALR retractors that keep tightening. Comfort suffers, so use drops. Many older tractors lack belts entirely.

Methods: Five farmers (ages 32-54) completed semi-structured interviews. The Agrarscouts network (64 participants) responded via an Instagram poll. Two safety experts provided technical assessments through personal meetings.

Results: Further action is needed to lower ejections in roll-overs, severe injuries: Fit more comfortable systems, such as new three-point belts for tractors or ELR retractors. Add reminders or interlocks that warn or limit driving when the belt is not fastened. Retrofit older tractors where belts are missing or poor. Support retrofits with grants. Align tractor rules with the Machinery Regulation so that better belts and warning systems become standard. Back this with clear campaigns and hands-on demos, e.g., a tilting-cab roll-over simulator.

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Target group 3: Researchers

Making farm safety work in Germany: priorities and learning that fit the job

Issue: German farming faces high risks. Workloads peak, the weather is tough, and many farmers are older. SVLFG promotes existing measures, yet daily uptake can lag. Despite strong support from statutory accident insurance, occupational safety is often delegated rather than owned by farms themselves.

Methods: A national survey gathered 111 responses via online and in-person SVLFG channels and the AgrarScouts network. Farmers ranked their priorities and learning preferences. Results were validated through an online meeting with German CoP and the AgrarScouts.

Results: Farmers ranked risk awareness/mindset as the top safety priority. Next came PPE use, then safe machinery and equipment. Time, money, and formal training ranked lower. For learning, farmers preferred peer discussions and one-to-one advice. Classroom formats and digital risk-tools came last. Practical actions are needed to promote stronger risk competence, higher uptake of proven measures, fewer injuries and healthier farms: Run group inspections with a workshop feel, instead of only one-farm visits. Cluster farms with similar risks. Inspect a host farm "officially", then guest farmers review their own yards and report back. Offer clear incentives, with enforcement as back-up. Use the alternative support model for regular refresher sessions. Ensure they are regional, well-moderated, with hands-on demos and peer exchange.

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Target group 3: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Ireland

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Ireland

Issue: Ireland's farm health and safety (FHS) framework is well-established, with leading roles for the Health and Safety Authority, Department of Agriculture and Teagasc. However, coordination within the framework is largely informal, data systems are fragmented, and integration of health, wellbeing, and farmer engagement is limited, reducing the effectiveness of policies across diverse farm types and regions

Method: SafeHabitus developed a structured method to map farm health and safety governance, which each country applied and adapted to its context. In Ireland, this involved desk research, expert interviews, an Expert IRL-Community of Practice meeting, evaluation as part of the National Policy Dialogue (NPD), and stakeholder consultations. The recommendations were finalised during a follow-up NPD.

Results: The recommendations aim to strengthen the existing Irish system by: (i) establishing a national data system for fatalities, injuries, and near-misses to guide evidence-informed interventions; (ii) developing an integrated, farmer-centred health and wellbeing support system to improve accessibility; (iii) strengthening education and lifelong learning through a National FHS Education and Training Platform; and (iv) formalising cross-sector coordination via a National FHS Coordination Group to align stakeholders and enhance strategic coordination for safer, healthier, and more resilient farm communities.

COP Ireland

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Target group 3: Researchers

Causes and Consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges: Machinery accidents among older farmers in Ireland

Issue: This study examines machinery accidents affecting older farmers in Ireland, where over half of all farm fatalities involve tractors and equipment. Irish farming is predominantly family-owned (96%), with farmers facing long hours, financial pressures, and an aging workforce. Older farmers (65+) are most at risk, particularly during busy seasons when time pressure is greatest.

Method: Research involved expert focus group of 11 participants including farmers, advisors, educators, academics, and policymakers. The focus group was analysed using the Socioecological Model, supported by analyst's expertise and observational fieldwork.

Results: Machinery accidents arise as older farmers put their own health and safety at risk by using their energy and wellbeing to bridge gaps in governance, labour, machinery, profits, time, or expertise. We identified three cycles heighten accident risk: (1) farmers are expected to be 'experts at everything,' (2) aging farm infrastructure and farmers' limited adaptation strategies after accidents can increase financial burden (3) a lack of generational renewal forces farmers to work into advanced age, with less help. Improving older farmers' safety therefore requires bridging structural gaps: improving generational renewal and succession, strengthening financial security, and fostering peer-to-peer expertise sharing and capacity building.

COP Ireland

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Target group 3: Researchers

Irish farmers' safety and engagement priorities

Issue: Ireland's farm safety system is coordinated by multiple organisations with different directives including the Health and Safety Authority, Department of Agriculture, and Teagasc that collaborate on the farm safety partnership to advance agricultural OHS. However, despite ongoing awareness and intervention efforts there were 16 farm fatalities from January to September, 2025. Understanding how farmers want to engage with safety supports is vital to prevent further fatalities.

Method: A survey conducted at agricultural events, colleges, and farms asked 129 farmers to rank their top safety priorities and preferred engagement methods. Participants were predominantly younger (65% aged 18-24) and involved in sheep, beef, or dairy (82%). An expert focus group with 11 stakeholders evaluated survey findings and identified implementation actions.

Results: The survey identified health and safety awareness and safe machinery as top priorities, while Peer-to-peer learning through discussion groups was farmers' preferred engagement method. Experts agreed many farmers have good general safety awareness but often lack specific knowledge (e.g. operating specific machinery). Even more, experts identified that equipment manufacturers are largely absent from safety governance despite farmers wanting safe, easy-to-operate machinery. Recommendations include (1) peer-to-peer safety education for specific tasks and equipment and (2) cooperation with equipment manufacturers in safety training.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Lithuania

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Lithuania

Issue: Lithuania's farm health and safety (FHS) policy is shaped by multiple actors but remains fragmented. Key regulators include the Ministry of Social Security and Labour, the Ministry of Health, the State Labour Inspectorate, and the State Food and Veterinary Service. Advisory services and community actors influence implementation, yet gaps persist in coordination and farmer engagement.

Method: SafeHabitus developed a structured method to map FHS governance, which was applied and adapted to the Lithuanian context. The Lithuanian approach included desk-based research to identify existing policies and governance structures, followed by an interview with two researchers-experts from Vytautas Magnus University, a Community of Practice (CoP) meeting to discuss actor map findings and finally, a Guided Evaluation of the draft actor map during the first National Policy Dialogue (NPD).

Results: To strengthen FHS in Lithuania, a national coordinating body should enhance cross-institutional collaboration. Expanding the role of advisory service providers can offer more targeted and practical support at the farm level. Clear communication tools tailored for smallholders and seasonal workers would help improve awareness and understanding of safety practices. Farmers' unions and peer networks should be formally involved in policy development to ensure inclusive representation. A national monitoring and evaluation framework could help track progress, while incentive-based mechanisms — such as financial rewards or tax benefits — may encourage greater compliance and proactive safety measures.

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Target group 3: Researchers

Understanding the Causes and Consequences of Work-Related Stress in Lithuanian Agriculture: Qualitative Insights and Pathways to Solutions

Issue: In Lithuania, as across the EU, farmers face high levels of work-related stress driven by long hours, financial insecurity, isolation, and demanding physical conditions. Insights from farmers and advisors highlight urgent challenges and the need for organisational and policy interventions to support safer, more sustainable farming livelihoods.

Method: This study applied the Socioecological Model (SEM) to explore stress factors in Lithuanian agriculture across individual, interpersonal, organisational, community, and policy levels. Four semi-structured interviews were conducted with two farmers and two agricultural advisors, focusing on stress sources, consequences, and coping strategies. Notes were taken collaboratively by an interviewer and notetaker, ensuring accuracy. Data were thematically coded using the SEM framework to classify stressors and outcomes across levels.

Results: Semi-structured interviews showed that stress in Lithuanian agriculture stems from multiple socioecological levels. While organisational weaknesses and policy shortcomings were identified as major structural causes, consequences were most visible at the individual level, including fatigue, anxiety, and health risks. Family burdens, lack of substitute workers, and negative community perceptions further intensified stress. Participants proposed solutions focused on strengthening associations, advisory services, and public communication, alongside fairer taxation, pension reform, and insurance schemes. Overall, tackling agricultural stress requires coordinated organisational and policy interventions to reduce individual burdens and enhance sector resilience.

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rural development organisations

Target group 3: Researchers

Occupational safety and health analysis in Lithuanian agriculture

Issue: Occupational safety and health in Lithuania are defined by law, yet no dedicated framework exists for farm safety. While multiple institutions contribute to regulation and support, responsibilities remain fragmented. Farmers, families, and workers therefore face persistent risks, underscoring the need for stronger coordination and farmer-focused safety measures in agriculture.

Method: Data were collected through 66 questionnaires completed by Lithuanian farmers and farm workers, both in person (20) and online via the EU Survey platform (46). Paper questionnaires were distributed during the “Ką pasėsi” agricultural fair at Vytautas Magnus University and during farm visits. The survey, translated from Teagasc, was adapted for Lithuanian respondents. Questions captured demographics, farm roles, and sectoral distribution of agricultural activities.

Results: Survey findings show that farmers prioritise safe machinery and greater awareness of health and safety risks, with personal protective equipment and time management also important. Respondents prefer learning through individual consultations and classroom training, while passive methods were less valued. The Community of Practice confirmed these priorities, additionally stressing mandatory training, youth education, and increased media attention. Overall, results highlight the need for awareness campaigns, improved access to safe equipment, personalised advisory services, and balanced regulatory and financial support.

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Target group 3: Farmers, farm workers and others exposed to the farm environment

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Poland

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Poland

Issue: In Poland, employees' right to health and life protection is ensured by the Constitution and Labour Code. Occupational health and safety (OHS) is regulated through general and sector-specific laws, especially in agriculture. While the Ministries lead national strategy, informal networks and local leaders strongly influence safety culture, shaping both good practices and safe habits.

Method: SafeHabitus developed a structured method to map farm health and safety governance, adapted by each country to its context. In Poland, this included desk research, Core Community of Practice discussions, and evaluation during the National Policy Dialogue (NPD). The mapping showed that various institutions could strongly influence agricultural occupational health and safety. However, discussions within the NPD have shown that the involvement of individual stakeholders governing these issues is uneven and sometimes too weak.

Results: Systematic cooperation between institutions like the Agricultural Social Insurance Fund, Agricultural Advisory Centres, and local and state authorities contributes to reducing the number of accidents and improving safety on farms. However, advisory services should play a larger role in knowledge dissemination. Initiatives could expand via the National Rural Network and Local Action Groups. Education on occupational health and safety should be integrated into school curricula. Financial support for micro and small farms, including safety-related investments, should be increased, with the Agency for Restructuring and Modernisation of Agriculture overseeing funding.

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Target group 3: Researchers

Understanding the causes and consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges in Poland

Issue: In Poland, as in many other countries, agricultural work accidents most often result from routine, haste, fatigue, and poor technical condition of machinery. They lead to injuries, farmers' disabilities, and disruptions in farm operations and family life. Increasing hazard awareness, providing practical training, and maintaining equipment in proper technical condition are crucial.

Method: Data were collected through semi-structured online interviews to enable easy recording and transcription. Participants included a small farm manager, a large farm worker, a farm advisor, a labour inspector, and a labour sociologist. Interviews were conducted during periods of reduced fieldwork, mainly at the end of summer, to suit farmers' schedules. To examine stress factors in Polish agriculture, data were thematically coded using the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) framework across individual, interpersonal, organisational, community, and policy levels.

Results: According to most respondents, farm accidents result from routine, underestimating risks, heavy workloads, rushing, and stress, which lead to unsafe behaviours. Additional factors include poorly maintained machinery, often due to financial constraints, and insufficient supervision of children on the farm. Consequences include injuries, disruption of farm operations and family life, and financial losses. Reducing these risks requires safety training, raising awareness, better work organization, use of checklists, financial support for machinery replacement, organized childcare during intensive work periods, and mandatory school education on farm health and safety.

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Polish farmers' safety and engagement priorities

Issue: Farm-related injuries in Poland have declined due to improved risk monitoring and education, though underreporting on individual farms persists. Strengthening safety requires farmer training, early school education in farm safety, modern technologies, and better health and psychological support, alongside family involvement in safety programs and financial aid for machine modernization.

Method: Data were collected through direct interviews with farmers during meetings and events in cooperation with field workers from the Agricultural Social Insurance Fund (KRUS) and through an online survey. Most responses came from southern Poland. Respondents, mostly aged 35–54 and almost equally male and female, were mainly farmers or their family members managing field crop farms, less often livestock or mixed farms. The average farmland area was 115 ha, but most farms were relatively small.

Results: Survey results show that most respondents consider hazard awareness, safe equipment, and personal protective gear crucial for farm safety. Training courses, advisory services, and group discussions were seen as the best sources of safety knowledge. CoP experts confirmed these findings, emphasizing the need for systemic education, better coordination of safety initiatives, modernization support, and psychological training such as mindfulness. Strengthening cooperation among agricultural, educational, and medical institutions can further enhance farmers' awareness, mental resilience, and overall work safety.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Romania

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Romania

Issue: The farm health and safety (FHS) policy and governance in Romania are at an early stage of development. The sector is predominantly regulated by general occupational safety frameworks, as specific directives tailored for agricultural work are scarce.

Method: By triangulating multiple research tools (e.g., desk research, focus groups), we developed and validated the FHS Actor Map – a visual representation of relevant organisational and institutional actors, considering their importance, influence, and interest in FHS. This process highlighted the need to improve the policy and governance landscape in Romania through the establishment of dedicated FHS institutions and organisations, the development of an integrated framework with clearly defined institutional roles and coordinating responsibilities, and the implementation of tailored educational programmes and awareness campaigns for farmers and farm workers, who have significant legal responsibilities regarding occupational safety.

Results: Particular attention should be given to small farms and some specific types of workers active in the sector (e.g., daily workers, family members), as these groups are exposed to increased risks due to lower levels of training and risk awareness, as well as limited health insurance coverage. Addressing these gaps is crucial for building a more effective and comprehensive farm safety governance framework in Romania.

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Understanding the Causes and Consequences of Farm Accidents in Romania: Qualitative Insights and Pathways to Solutions

Issue: A thorough analysis of occupational safety in agriculture is needed in Romania, and the perspectives of farmers and other relevant stakeholders are essential for understanding the causes and consequences of work-related accidents on farms. To achieve this objective, SafeHabitus employed qualitative tools from the social sciences (e.g., focus groups, multi-stakeholder thematic discussions) and collected empirical evidence regarding work practices and safety challenges in Romania.

Method: The results indicate several key factors to be considered: the lack of knowledge about occupational health and safety among many agricultural workers, which translates into the acceptance of unnecessary risks; extended working hours and fatigue reduce the ability of farmers and farm workers to accurately assess the danger of specific tasks; challenges in hiring additional staff and difficulties in acquiring newer machinery, which is often very expensive. Among the main consequences identified were injuries and illnesses affecting farmers and farm workers, which lead to significant economic and emotional costs for all those active in the sector, as well as manpower shortages and low attractiveness of agricultural work.

Results: Urgent and tailored solutions are needed to foster a more sustainable safety culture. Awareness campaigns and improved access to finance for safer machinery and protective equipment are essential steps. Moreover, creating supportive forums for farmers to discuss safety issues, share experiences, and connect with experts can significantly enhance practices at the farm level.

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Target group 3: Researchers

Key Measures to Enhance Farm Safety: Evaluation, Prioritization, and Preferences of Stakeholders in Romania

Issue: To enhance farm safety in Romania, attention should be paid to stakeholders' evaluations of the challenges in the sector, their prioritization of potential solutions, as well as their preferences for extending knowledge about farm safety. We designed a social research framework for collecting and processing data focused on these key components of any social innovation process through triangulation of survey results with thematic discussions within SafeHabitus Communities of Practice.

Method: Our empirical outcomes indicate that the main priorities are linked to: (1) increasing awareness of health and safety risks in farming; (2) extending the use of personal protective equipment; and (3) creating a culture of support to farm safely from family, friends, and significant others. In Romania, the preferred modalities for learning about farm safety can be built around: (1) group discussions with other farmers, advisors, and specialists; (2) learning through dedicated courses; and (3) one-to-one support from an advisor or specialist. Additionally, stakeholders emphasized the need to develop specific programs to stimulate discussions on health and safety topics and stressed the importance of involving young farmers and students in the field through participatory methods.

Results: By intersecting these results, we can highlight stakeholder openness to solutions that effectively engage farmers in the process of building a safer culture of farming in Romania through dedicated training and campaigns, as well as collaborative groups.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Slovakia

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Policy and Governance Framework in Slovakia

Issue: Farming is one of the most dangerous jobs in Slovakia, but accident data covers only employed workers and excludes family members. Current health and safety rules are general Occupational health and safety laws, not tailored to agriculture. There is no national strategy or central platform to coordinate farm health and safety (FHS) activities. Farmers have little influence over policymaking, despite being the most affected.

Method: SafeHabitus applied a structured mapping method, including desk research, expert consultation, and a National Policy Dialogue (NPD). Actors were classified by type and assessed for their influence and interest. This revealed that farmers and cooperatives are undervalued in their influence and should play a more active role.

Results:

Key recommendations include:

Create a national FHS coordination platform co-led by the Ministries of Labour and Agriculture.

Develop agriculture-specific safety guidelines and improve data collection to include family labour.

Strengthen farmer participation through advisory committees and training.

Expand awareness-raising activities and build networks with cooperatives and NGOs.

These steps will make FHS policy more effective, targeted and responsive to real farm needs.

COP Slovakia

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Target Audience

Target group 1: Policymakers, public authorities

Target group 2: Advisors, innovation support services

Target group 3: Researchers

Understanding the causes and consequences of Farm Health and Safety Challenges

Issue: This technical note examines the main causes and consequences of occupational health and safety (OHS) challenges in Slovak agricultural enterprises, focusing on small and medium-sized farms. The study assesses farmers' awareness of OHS requirements, their perceptions of obligations, and the practical barriers that limit effective compliance in everyday work. Interviews with farmers, an OHS advisor, and a safety technician provided insights into common attitudes and challenges.

Method: Findings show that administrative demands, limited time, and the view that some regulations are impractical lead to partial or inconsistent implementation. Many farmers regard OHS measures as bureaucratic tasks rather than preventive tools, and training is often seen as formal rather than useful. Experts note that this mindset contributes to underestimated risks and missed opportunities for meaningful prevention.

Results: Overall, this approach reduces productivity and weakens engagement in effective safety practices. The study highlights the need for clearer rules, practical tools, simpler administration, and training that reflects real farm conditions. Improving OHS should be viewed as an investment in long-term farm resilience and performance. Such an approach can strengthen understanding of real workplace hazards, support better decision-making, encourage consistent safety practices, and help farms integrate OHS principles into routine operations without excessive administrative burden today.

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Slovak farmers' safety and engagement priorities

Issue: Farm safety in Slovakia is often overlooked due to financial pressure, time constraints and limited awareness.

Method: A survey of 50 farmers, farm workers and agricultural students was conducted as a part of SafeHabitus project.

Results: Results showed that the highest priority for improving safety is increasing awareness of farm health and safety risks. Improving machinery and equipment safety was ranked second, followed by the use of personal protective equipment. Participants preferred one-to-one advice from specialists and learning in groups with other farmers. Digital tools and risk assessment booklets were less popular. These findings confirm that Slovak agriculture needs practical, personalised solutions that fit real farm conditions. Recommendations include integrating health and safety training into agricultural school curricula, expanding access to on-farm advisory services, supporting peer-learning platforms and modernising machinery and infrastructure. A national strategy could coordinate education, advisory services and investment support. Improving farm safety will protect workers' health, reduce accidents and make farming more sustainable. Engagement of farmers, workers, students and policymakers is essential to create solutions that are practical and widely used.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Slovenia

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety (FHS) Policy and Governance Framework in Slovenia

Issue: Slovenian Occupational health and Safety (OHS) legislation follows EU directives but is not specifically tailored to agriculture. Most people working on farms are not legally required to comply with OHS regulations, as they are not formally employed in agriculture. The number of fatalities is high, and the accident rate in the sector is above the national average. No actor coordinates FHS. Advisory capacity is minimal. Key ILO conventions for FHS have not yet been ratified.

Method: Farm health and safety governance was mapped using the SafeHabitus structured approach. Desk research identified policies and actors. An expert meeting in December 2024 refined the results. The Community of Practice applied a Quadruple Helix and an Importance-Influence-Interests Matrix, and validated and expanded the list of actors via email. The first National Policy Dialogue in March 2025 explored roles, responsibilities, and gaps. This resulted in a consolidated actor map and a shared diagnosis of weak coordination, low engagement of some key agencies, and low advisory capacity for FHS.

Results: The Ministry of Labour, Family and Social Affairs should take over the coordination of FHS provision, supported by the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food, and the Ministry of Health. A database of injuries and illnesses on farms should be established. Advice should also be strengthened: OHS engineers should be trained for FHS, a department for agricultural activities should be established within the OHS Chamber, and annual field visits and training for FHS should be introduced. A replacement service should be introduced on farms. Measures for tractor safety must be consistently implemented. The Farmers' Union must be involved in these activities. Existing initiatives (veterinarians, foresters, the "PoljaMoči" project) must be used to raise awareness, ensure periodic inspections, and strengthen skills.

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Mental Health of Farmers in Slovenia

Issue: Slovenian farmers face heavy workloads, market precarity, family tensions, and stigma that suppress help-seeking. Digital “always-on” monitoring extends vigilance into rest time. Consequences include burnout, depressive states, strained relationships, and presenteeism; risks and impacts are gendered and vary by farm size and dependence on farming income.

Method: Six qualitative interviews (four farmers, two practitioners; age 23 - 46) explored causes, consequences, and solutions through a socio-ecological lens (individual, family, farm/organisation, community, system).

Results: Repeating mechanisms drive distress: an overwork-stigma loop; a precarity cascade (prices, debt, time scarcity); isolation and invisibility in small communities; and stress amplification through digitalisation. Barriers include distance, limited transport, fragmented services, and cultural scripts of stoicism.

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Risk management and support for Slovenian farmers

Issue: Farm work in Slovenia remains hazardous, with persistent fatal tractor incidents and other injuries. Although awareness of safe practices is high, farmers' day-to-day behaviour often lags behind, particularly regarding seat belt use on tractors.

Method: We surveyed 60 people connected to farming (farmers, family members, workers, and agronomy students) using paper and online questionnaires, then discussed the findings with Slovenia's Community of Practice (CoP).

Results: Respondents rated personal protective equipment highest for safer work, followed closely by safer machinery and risk awareness. Classroom courses were the preferred training format, complemented by peer discussion, learning by doing, and one-to-one specialist support. Reading in agri-media, simple risk assessment tools, and informal family advice scored lower. CoP members considered some answers socially desirable and highlighted a gap between knowing and doing—most notably, not wearing tractor seat belts.

What works in practice. Combine classroom teaching with experiential learning (including tractor and implement simulators), regular refresher sessions in all advisory training, and sustained awareness campaigns (e.g. police spot checks with warnings and leaflets). Begin safety education early with children. Progress requires stronger leadership from the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food, and coordination with labour and health authorities to embed systematic, long-term behaviour change.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACTS: COP Spain

Strengthening the Farm Health and safety Policy and Governance Framework in Spain

Issue: Spain has a broad framework for occupational health and safety in agriculture, anchored in national laws and coordinated action plans. However, gaps remain in enforcement and participation. Key challenges include limited inspection capacity, lack of national housing standards for seasonal workers, and the weak representation of migrant voices in decision-making.

Method: SafeHabitus applied a common mapping method across countries. In Spain, the process focused on the Huelva berry sector, using desk research and interviews with local advisers. An expert meeting with Spain's Community of Practice helped build the actor map. This was validated in the February 2025 National Policy Dialogue, which brought together stakeholders from all sectors.

Results: Recommendations include: creating national housing standards with verifiable criteria and a compliance registry; strengthening multilingual inspection teams and using risk-based prioritisation; developing a specific strategy for migrant workers with clear goals and resources; and establishing formal consultation channels to involve seasonal workers in OSH decisions. These steps aim to improve transparency, worker safety, and coordination between public and private actors in Spain's farming sector.

COP Spain

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Housing Conditions of Temporary Migrant Workers in Huelva: The Safety Challenge in Informal Settlements and Farm Accommodations

Issue: In Huelva, southern Spain, thousands of temporary migrant farmworkers—mainly from Morocco, Romania, and Sub-Saharan Africa—face unsafe and degrading housing conditions. Many live in informal shanty settlements or overcrowded farm accommodations without water or electricity. This situation stems from a lack of affordable housing, exploitative labor models, and weak institutional oversight, generating serious health, safety, and social consequences.

Method: The study used a qualitative approach based on six semi-structured interviews conducted in Huelva during the 2024–2025 berry harvest season. Participants included NGO representatives and local agricultural producers. A purposive sampling strategy ensured diverse stakeholder perspectives. Interviews were recorded and thematically analyzed using the Socio-Ecological Model, allowing classification of causes, consequences, and solutions at individual, interpersonal, community, and institutional levels.

Results: Findings reveal that lack of decent housing, employer neglect, and migrant irregular status are key causes. Consequences include poor hygiene, mental stress, exclusion from services, and reputational risks for the agricultural sector. Solutions proposed involve legal regularization, creation of dignified housing alternatives, and multi-actor coordination between NGOs, authorities, and producers. Collective efforts, improved oversight, and public-private housing initiatives are vital to replace unsafe settlements with safe, humane living conditions.

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Agricultural Workplace Safety for Migrant Workers in Huelva: Findings from the SafeHabitus Survey (Spanish CoP)

Issue: Migrant agricultural workers in Huelva face heightened vulnerability to workplace accidents due to insufficient protective equipment, limited staffing, intense work rhythms and language barriers. Although they are essential to the berry sector, their needs and voices remain underrepresented in safety governance, resulting in policies that often fail to address their real working conditions.

Method: A survey was conducted with 40 participants, mostly migrant seasonal workers and some farm owners or managers, using an online questionnaire disseminated through NGOs and Ethical Trade Forums. The original SafeHabitus tool was translated into Spanish, and community organisations provided linguistic support in Arabic, French and other languages. The survey captured demographic data and gathered respondents' rankings of safety priorities and preferred learning methods, ensuring that findings reflected real experiences across Huelva's agricultural towns.

Results: Respondents prioritised access to proper PPE and having sufficient help or time to work safely. Mid-level priorities included safe machinery, financial resources for improvements and training support. Awareness-raising campaigns ranked lowest. Workers preferred practical, hands-on learning, followed by formal courses, simple risk-assessment tools and informal peer discussions. Specialist advice, group forums and written materials were less valued. Overall, workers emphasised tangible safety improvements and accessible, practical training adapted to their language and context.

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PRACTICE ABSTRACT: Social conditionality

Social Conditionality in CAP: Implementation Challenges and Coverage Gaps for Policy Makers

Social Conditionality (SC) links CAP subsidies to compliance with EU labour standards for the first time, but faces significant implementation challenges. While the policy signals EU commitment to decent work in agriculture, two critical factors limit its potential impact:

1. It excludes key policy instruments, e.g. funding for Producer Organisations, which are common in labour-intensive sectors like fruit/vegetables and wine that receive operational programme support rather than area-based payments; and
2. Self-employed farmers and family workers (68% of the agricultural workforce) are not covered. Additionally, national labour inspectorates face capacity constraints, and temporary employment agencies create enforcement gaps since they employ workers but do not receive CAP payments.

Member States have adopted varied implementation approaches, risking intra-EU competitive imbalances. Policy officials should invest in coordination infrastructure between labour inspectorates and paying agencies, develop clear temporary agency protocols, and commission research on actual workforce coverage. At the Member State level, additional advisory supports are necessary to ensure farmers are aware of the details of the regulation and the practical steps that they can take to ensure compliance.

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https://www.safehabit.us/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/SafeHabit.us_Social-conditionality_TN.pdf

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PRACTICE ABSTRACT: Using Tax Policy to Accelerate Farm Safety Investment

Using Tax Policy to Accelerate Farm Safety Investment: Ireland's Equipment Allowance Scheme

Ireland has developed an innovative farm safety scheme using accelerated tax depreciation allowances to incentivise equipment investment. Rather than traditional grants, farmers can write off qualifying safety equipment at 50% annually instead of the standard 12.5%, significantly reducing real investment costs through enhanced tax relief.

The scheme operates under national tax law whilst maintaining EU State Aid compliance through the Agriculture Block Exemption Regulation. Farmers apply to the Department of Agriculture for certificates confirming their equipment purchases qualify for accelerated allowances. The scheme covers 22 equipment categories including preventative measures (hydraulic jacking systems, chemical storage), accessibility adaptations (wheelchair lifts, modified controls), and infrastructure improvements (livestock handling facilities, flood lighting).

Key features include individual limits of €500,000 per farmer, annual national budget of €5 million, and quality assurance through CE marking requirements. Equipment must be purchased between 2021-2026, with applications by December 2026 on a first-come, first-served basis.

This approach demonstrates how tax policy can address agricultural challenges whilst leveraging private investment rather than direct public funding. The comprehensive framework provides a replicable model for other EU Member States seeking to enhance farm safety through fiscal incentives, particularly benefiting farmers with sufficient taxable income to maximise depreciation benefits.

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Contribution to expected outcomes

The library of 35 Practice Abstracts presented in this document, and related Technical Notes published in the SafeHabitus Knowledge Hub, provide a comprehensive overview of policy and governance frameworks, causal and consequential factors of key challenges, and priorities of farming populations on farm health and safety (FHS) across 11 EU member states. This body of work contributes directly to the objectives that were set for the project.

Expected outcomes

Outcome 1, *enhance understanding and awareness by policy makers, farmer's organisations, trade unions and health authorities of the potential solutions to the health and safety challenges faced by farmers and farm workers* through a multi-stakeholder approach across 11 EU Member States that engaged key actors in participatory actor mapping, the project identified actors, stakeholders and organisations that shape farm health and safety governance and policy. Insights from this process will inform co-created recommendations to strengthen national policy and governance frameworks. A similar multi-stakeholder approach was used to identify the safety and engagement priorities of farmers and farmworkers (PA/TN 10), and the causes and consequences of key farm safety challenges (PA/TN 9). Through continuous engagement, these tasks strengthened stakeholder awareness of key safety challenges and priorities for farmers across member states. The recommendations will be disseminated via the SafeHabitus Knowledge Hub (Task 1.2), supporting evidence-based awareness and decision-making among policy-makers and practitioners.

Outcome 2, *improved policy and governance frameworks favouring safer and more inclusive working environments for farmers and farm workers*: by using the findings from guided mapping of and evaluation of the farm health and safety policy and governance framework, and the findings of the survey on farmers safety and engagement priorities, to inform evidence-based recommendations strengthening national policy and governance systems and supporting the development of more effective national and EU-level policy and governance measures (WP6).

Outcome 4, *Improved health, safety and labour conditions in farming thanks to better performing European and national policy and legal frameworks and innovative bottom-up initiatives*: by improving the knowledge transfer through co-design approaches and ensuring the visibility and strong involvement of priorities of the target population: the bottom-up initiatives in PA's 9-10 describe a co-designed approach to empirical research that highlights the experiences and needs of key populations of farmers and farmworkers to the relevant policymakers and governance authorities. These tasks also describe potential solutions at multiple levels (from individual responses to community interventions and policy changes) to improve the occupational health of these workers.

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